

THE IMPORTANCE OF E171 DYE IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY AND ITS EFFECT ON THE BODY

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Abstract

TiO₂ (E 171) is a pigment used to alter the visual properties of food and beverages. It is also used in cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and toothpastes, which means that we may also come in contact with the substance while taking medicines or using personal hygiene products such as toothpastes or mouthwashes. Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nanoparticles (NPs) have been widely applied in various industrial fields, such as electronics, packaging, food, and cosmetics. Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is commonly applied to enhance the white colour and brightness of food products. TiO₂ is also used as white pigment in other products such as toothpaste. A small fraction of the pigment is known to be present as nanoparticles (NPs). Submicron-sized TiO₂ particles, in Europe listed as E 171, are widely used as a food additive although the relevant risk assessment has never been satisfactorily completed. For example, it is not possible to derive a safe daily intake of TiO₂ from the available long-term feeding studies in rodents. Also, the use of TiO₂ particles in the food sector leads to highest exposures in children, but only few studies address the vulnerability of this particular age group. Extrapolation of animal studies to humans is also problematic due to knowledge gaps as to local gastrointestinal effects of TiO₂ particles, primarily on the mucosa and the gut-associated lymphoid system. Tissue distributions after oral administration of TiO₂ differ from other exposure routes, thus limiting the relevance of data obtained from inhalation or parenteral injections. Such difficulties and uncertainties emerging in the retrospective assessment of TiO₂ particles exemplify the need for a fit-to-purpose data requirement for the future evaluation of novel nano-sized or submicron-sized particles added deliberately to food.

Keywords: E171, Titanium dioxide, Nanoparticles

Introduction

Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is a naturally occurring metal oxide and is one of the first engineered nanomaterials most commonly used in daily consumer products, including food¹. The TiO₂ food additive, referred to as E171 in the European Union (EU), is commonly used as a whitening and brightening agent in confectionary (candies and chewing gum), white sauces and icing¹⁻³. The Food and Drug Administration approved the use of food-grade TiO₂ in 1966 with the stipulation that TiO₂ levels must not exceed 1% of the food weight⁴. In Europe, the current EU Directive 94/36/EC authorizes the use of E171 in foodstuff without establishing an acceptable daily intake level by the Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives, based on TiO₂ absorption considered to be very low⁵. Nevertheless, the common use of E171 leads to significant levels of daily dietary intake of nanoparticulate matter among humans¹. Indeed, E171 batches show broad size distributions of TiO₂ primary particles [1].

Titanium dioxide is a common additive in many food, personal care, and other consumer products used by people, which after use can enter the sewage system and,

subsequently, enter the environment as treated effluent discharged to surface waters or biosolids applied to agricultural land, incinerated wastes, or landfill solids. This study quantifies the amount of titanium in common food products, derives estimates of human exposure to dietary (nano-) TiO₂, and discusses the impact of the nanoscale fraction of TiO₂ entering the environment. The foods with the highest content of TiO₂ included candies, sweets, and chewing gums. Among personal care products, toothpastes and select sunscreens contained 1% to >10% titanium by weight. While some other cremes contained titanium, despite being colored white, most shampoos, deodorants, and shaving creams contained the lowest levels of titanium (<0.01 µg/mg). For several high-consumption pharmaceuticals, the titanium content ranged from below the instrument detection limit (0.0001 µg Ti/mg) to a high of 0.014 µg Ti/mg. Electron microscopy and stability testing of food-grade TiO₂ (E171) suggests that approximately 36% of the particles are less than 100 nm in at least one dimension and that it readily disperses in water as fairly stable colloids. However, filtration of water solubilized consumer products and personal care products indicated that less than 5% of the titanium was able to pass through 0.45 or 0.7 µm pores. Two white paints contained 110 µg Ti/mg while three sealants (i.e., prime coat paint) contained less titanium (25 to 40 µg Ti/mg). This research showed that, while many white-colored products contained titanium, it was not a prerequisite. Although several of these product classes contained low amounts of titanium, their widespread use and disposal down the drain and eventually to wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) deserves attention. A Monte Carlo human exposure analysis to TiO₂ through foods identified children as having the highest exposures because TiO₂ content of sweets is higher than other food products and that a typical exposure for a US adult may be on the order of 1 mg Ti per kilogram body weight per day. Thus, because of the millions of tons of titanium-based white pigment used annually, testing should focus on food-grade TiO₂ (E171) rather than that adopted in many environmental health and safety tests (i.e., P25), which is used in much lower amounts in products less likely to enter the environment (e.g., catalyst supports, photocatalytic coatings) [2].

As a bulk material, titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is primarily used as a pigment because of its brightness, high refractive index, and resistance to discoloration. The global production of TiO₂ for all uses is in the millions of tons per year. Nearly 70% of all TiO₂ produced is used as a pigment in paints, but it is also used as a pigment in glazes, enamels, plastics, paper, fibers, foods, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and toothpastes.¹ Other TiO₂ uses include antimicrobial applications, catalysts for air and water purification, medical applications, and energy storage. Recently, more attention has been given to the use of TiO₂ as a nanomaterial. In 2005, the global production of nanoscale TiO₂ was estimated to be 2000 t worth \$70 million;² approximately, 1300 t was used in personal care products (PCPs) such as topical sunscreens and cosmetics. By 2010, the production had increased to 5000 t, and it is expected to continue to increase until at least 2025 with greater reliance upon nanosize TiO₂. Consequentially, many sources of nanoscale TiO₂ could result in human exposure and entrance of this material into the environment (air, water, or soil compartments) [3,4].

TiO₂-containing materials are produced in a range of primary particle sizes. Many applications of TiO₂ would benefit from smaller primary particle sizes, and the percentage of TiO₂ that is produced in or near the nano range is expected to increase exponentially. TiO₂ nanoparticles are generally synthesized with a crystalline structure (anatase, rutile, or brookite, each of which has unique properties). The most common procedure for synthesis of

TiO₂ nanoparticles utilize the hydrolysis of titanium (Ti) salts in an acidic solution. Use of chemical vapor condensation or nucleation from sol-gel can control the structure, size, and shape of the TiO₂ nanoparticles.^{8,9} To increase photostability and prevent aggregation, TiO₂ nanomaterials (particles, tubes, wires, etc.) are commonly coated with aluminum, silicon, or polymers^[4,5].

TiO₂ nanomaterials in foods, consumer products, and household products are discharged as feces/urine, washed off of surfaces, or disposed of to sewage that enters wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Although WWTPs are capable of removing the majority of nanoscale and larger-sized TiO₂ from influent sewage, TiO₂ particles measuring between 4 and 30 nm were still found in the treated effluent. These nanomaterials are then released to surface waters, where they can interact with living organisms. One study monitoring TiO₂ nanomaterials found the highest concentrations in river water to be directly downstream of a WWTP.¹⁴ TiO₂ nanomaterials removed from sewage through association with bacteria may still end up in the environment if the biomass is land applied ^[6,7].

Although the release of TiO₂ nanomaterials to the environment has been shown qualitatively, quantification of how much is released is difficult. It is impossible to determine all sources or measure the amount of released TiO₂ nanomaterials, which is why emissions are often modeled to better predict the impact of TiO₂ nanomaterials on the environment. The same difficulty applies to the assessment of human exposure, as estimated uptake rates of different types of nanoparticles range from 0% to 8.5% depending on type, size, and shape of the nanoparticles ^[8,9,10].

Toxicity studies mainly report a risk from nanoparticulate TiO₂ due to inhalation (inflammation and possible link to asthma), but titania has also been linked to Crohn's disease from gastrointestinal intake and it has been classified as a possibly carcinogen.^{18–21} However, a risk assessment has not been published yet and care has to be taken when comparing exposure to effect. Not only have modifications been reported to have diverging toxicological properties (anatase is 100 times more toxic than rutile in the nanoparticulate form) but also coatings, size, and shape modify the toxicity of nanoparticles, and only a small number of them have been tested. Once in the environment, even less is known about how TiO₂ nanomaterials affect organisms, although nanosized TiO₂ has been shown to inhibit growth of algae and bioaccumulate in *Daphnia magna*. However, several studies have indicated that TiO₂ tends to be less hazardous to organisms than other nanomaterials such as multiwall carbon nanotubes, nanocerium oxide, and nanozinc oxide. Previously, primary particle size was generally accepted as a large factor in toxicity, with smaller particles tending to be more toxic. However, recent studies have shown that particle size is only a single (and perhaps minor) factor influencing the toxicity of nanoparticles. Risk assessment of certain nanomaterials is still quite difficult because nanotoxicology studies rarely have enough reliable information on the physicochemical characteristics of the nanoparticles tested ^[10,11].

Many fate and transport as well as toxicity studies have used a readily available TiO₂ nanomaterial (Evonik Degussa P25) because the primary crystals are <50 nm in size and uncoated. P25 is advertised as "titanium dioxide without pigment properties". On the basis of information on the manufacturer's Web site, P25 is used primarily as a photocatalyst, catalyst carrier, and heat stabilizer for silicon rubber. This material is agglomerated in the dry powder state and readily aggregates to several hundred nanometers in water. However, usage of TiO₂

in the food, beverage, and paint markets dwarfs the usage of P25. For example, food-grade TiO₂ (referred to as E171) is purchased by the ton and is available as synthetic forms of anatase, rutile, and others. Only one study reports the titanium content of a few commercial products; we know very little about size or surface properties of E171 forms of these TiO₂s in comparison with the vast amount of data on P25 even though E171 and other commercially used whiteners represent the majority of TiO₂-containing materials that enter the ecosystem today [9,12].

This paper aims to begin filling the large knowledge gaps that exist regarding commonly used sources of TiO₂ materials. We obtained a broad spectrum of commercial products that either listed titanium dioxide on the label or had a “white” color and quantified the titanium content. Selected products were further characterized by electron microscopy. Using this new and already existing TiO₂ data, a human exposure analysis was conducted that indicates children may be disproportionately exposed to higher levels of all sizes of TiO₂. Finally, characteristics of E171 were compared against those of the titanium observed in food products and against those of P25 in an attempt to argue that greater efforts to elucidate fate and transport are needed for materials containing E171[8,11,12].

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